

THE FOREIGN POLICY OF THE KOKAND KHAN MUHAMMADALIKHAN IS ON THE EXAMPLE OF CHINA.

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Annotation: this article focuses on the foreign policy of the Kokand Khan Muhammadalikhan with China through Koshgar, the migration of the Koshgar people to the Kokand Khanate.

Key words: Kokand, Koshgar, Uygur, contract, Pekin, tradition, East Turkistan, Sin, manchjur, Jakhangirkhujatura, Ghazi, foreign policy.

The history of Uzbekistan has an ancient and rich history, and our people have gone a very big and laborious way. It was on this road that low-high, from "Sivilization" to "Renaissance", followed a very arduous route from "Renaissance" to Russian invasion. Our people have very many righteous Kings Enlightened statesmen and mature scientists. Of the invincible warlords, Ghazi saw the rulers. It is notable for its time and has left an indelible mark on history. "Muboriziddin val Mansur Muhammadalikhanghazi binni Umaron" is a clear example of this. Muhammadalikhan introduced very great cultural educational reforms in his time and added his worthy xissas to poetry and history to science. During the " Ghazi " era, mosques and madrasas were built. Coins were minted. Many ditches were dug. In foreign policy, it was advisable to establish relations with many countries. And sought to strengthen the established ties. Muhammadalikhan maintained contacts with countries such as Turkey, Bukhara, Russia, and India. Conducted a huge number of military campaigns. In a word, biln said that Muhammadalikhan among the people "Ghazi or "Madali" i.e. the source of justice with the names of to gain fame.

Muhammadalikhan, Khan of Kokand, finds the center of the Khanate in Kokand in 1806-1810. His Father Is Amir Umarchan, His Mother Is Mohlaroyim, His Uncle Is Olimkhan, His Younger Brother Is Sultan Mahmud Khan, Abdullahji, His Wife Is Uluqkhan, His Father-In-Law. Olimkhan, Whose Children Are Muhammadaminbek. [1. 21 b.]. The Khan of Kokand Muhammadalikhan was elevated to the Khanate throne at the age of 14 in 1822-1823 after the death of his father Umarchan by Kasimbeklarbegi, Shaykh-ul Islam Masumkhan Tora and Domulla Zakirkhoja on the Blessed Friday, December 29, 1822. [2. 16 b.].

The Kokand Khanate conducts trade relations with the Chinese state Khanate through Eastern Turkestan. Because the Qoshgar Transitway was important for the time. The main reason for the struggle between the Kokand Khanate and China, for which the main gate was Qoshgar i.e. East Turkestan, is due to the ownership of the territory. The area is on the main trade corridor from China to the West. East Turkestan was divided into two natural geographical zones by Mount Tyan-Shan. While the northern part is Jungoria, the southern part is called Ettisuv, Qoshgar. The markets in the cities of qoshgarh are crowded, and they are adjacent to trade roads from different sides. Chinese merchants from the East, tatar merchants from Russia

from the North and Kokand, Bukhara merchants from the West brought and sold their products here. There were three main roads from Kokand to East Turkestan. The first is the most convenient and short route, which passes through the Terek pass from the mountains of Tyan-Shan and Oloy. The second is a safe, but long road that passes through Tashkent, Turkestan and Qulja. The third was a dangerous pass through the Pamirs and Badakhshan, the caravans traveled relatively little, and it is worth noting that through Qoshgar to present-day Pakistan and Hindestan during that period, the Baburis and petty Rojas reigned in these goddesses. Now the Qoshgar road for Kham Central Asia is very special. [3. 58 b.] the establishment of trade and diplomatic relations of the Khanate in the Manchurian state of Emperor Qoshgar the situation in the Manchurian state led to the occupation of Qoshgar by the manjurs and the arrival of Erdonabi from the Qooqan Khans to hokimyat in 1751-1754-1754-1762, the Qooqan Khanate was officially dependent on the Sin empire from 1758-1762 until the period of Muhammadaligazi. After erdonabi's death the throne in the Kokand Khanate, as in the Khiva Khanate, the era of the KHAM throne games continues until the Narbakhadi or Norbotakhan periods. Abdulhamidbek periods during the 1770s and 1800s, good neighborly relations with the Sinas are conducted. During the government of Olimbek(Khan) 1801-1809, Kham good neighborly relations are carried out. The expansion of the territorial Khanate during the 1809-1822 period during the umarkhan periods and the continuous expansion of the borders of the Kokand Khanate directly towards the Russian Empire and The Empire Of The Sin, like the Emir of Bukhara, will be somewhat controversial during the Umarkhan period, due to the fact that Umarkhan himself was awarded the title of Emir al muslimin The far-sighted Emir Umar Khan was eager to pursue a policy of peace as far as possible. [4. 41-43 B]

The situation becomes more serious by the time of the Khan of Kokand Muhammadalihan. The main reason for this was that Madalikhan's largest military action was carried out in Kashgar. The real reason for madalikhan's March to Qoshgar was the repeated flight of Jahangirkhoja to Qoshgar, who had been held captive in Qooqan since the time of his father. According to sources, the Kokand Khans were carrying a thousand yombi (200 yombi according to other sources) of silver from China for keeping Jahangirkhoja in Kokand. Jahangirkhoja and his loved ones were kept under the arrest of the Horde in Kokand during the Umar Khan period, and were treated well. But Madalikhan did not treat them well. They were not financially supported by the state. As a result, they had a somewhat difficult life. Jahangirkhoja then manages to escape to Qoshgar along with his nephew Thurahan Thura. But they are caught in the mountainous regions of Andijan and brought back to Kokand. The Torah is released, while Jahangirkhojani continues to be held in prison. But at this time, 1824, there will be a severe earthquake in the Fergana Valley. Muhammadhakim Khan Thura, however, gives this earthquake as 1822-1823. Jahangirkhoja takes advantage of the chaos in the earthquake and escapes again. This time the Escape is lucky for him. This time jahangirkhoja flees to Balkh and Badakhshan sides. There, he marries the daughter of a local governor, and after forming a mutual alliance with the local governors and gathering strength, begins a march with his army of two thousand men to Qoshgar in March 1825. His army included even 12 Englishmen. There were even those who came to join the Jahangirkhoja Army from all over Central Asia. But the Kyrgyz, unable to cope with the difficulties during the walk, turn back. In the spring of 1826, Jahangirkhoja's troops occupy the lands up to the Tomb of Sotuk Bugrokhan. This tomb becomes their residence, and whole neighbors begin to come

there, dissatisfied with the policies of the Sin Empire. The Chinese army sent here surrounded the tomb and met the geese in maglubat, but Jahangirkhoja survived for hiding in a tomb. Of course this March was carried out with the consent of Madalikhan. Madalikhan sent an army of 10,000 men to the March. This walk ends with little success for the Madalikhan. After that, Madalikhan of 1243/1827 – 1828 receives the title of self-Governor. We can learn about this from the silver coin madalikhan minted in 1243/1827-1828. On the front side of the coin minted in this year –the title of Muhammadalikhan Ghazi is written. After madalikhan returned to Kokand, the qoshgarites continued their war against the Chinese, capturing the entire western part of Sintszyan (Yangihisor, Yorkent, Khotan) and continuing their march westward (Turfan, Ghulja, Oqsuv). From then on, Jahangirkhoja's authority in Qoshgar was restored and he would rule there for quite some time. Muhammad Ali Khan in general, like the rulers before him, pursued an active foreign policy. The events in the neighbouring region of Qoshgar led him to act in the area and consequently to a tense turn of his relations with China. It should be noted that From 1692 to 1760, kadar Qoshgar was dominated by Khojas, descendants of Mahdumi a'zam. Jahangirkhan Thura, a descendant of Sayyid Khidoyatulloh Khoja (Ofoqkhoja) of the same generation, sets out from Kokand towards Qoshgar in 1826 with the aim of reconquering Qoshgar. After Jahangir Khan established his rule by freeing Thura Kashgar from Chinese rule, Muhammad Alikhan also enters Qoshqar with the Qooqan army and helps him consolidate power. But this reign would last only 9 months, ending after the Chinese invasion. Jahangirkhoja and his loved ones had been captured by Chinese troops and executed in Beijing in the summer of 1829. The Chinese at this point send an envoy to Madalikhan to try to agree to keep him from arming the Khojas against them. But Madalikhan refuses the offer of the Chinese and arranges a march to Qoshgar. Sources cite the lack of timely collection of taxes from the territories under the Khanate as the reason for this March, filling the Treasury for the next March. In the same year, a Chinese ambassador arrives in Kokand. In Kokand, the proposal of the Chinese ambassador is discussed and ambassadors are sent to Beijing under the leadership of Aalam pochcha. The ambassador is received with great pomp in Beijing. According to local muarrichs, Madalikhan had sent the following demands to the Chinese emperor: 1) release the Sayyids (Khoja)held captive in Beijing (because they are of prophetic descent; 2) surrender of Muslims in seven cities Qashqar for sharia-based Administration; 3) payment of silver from China as customs tax in the amount of 10 thousand yombi each year. Madalikhan's second march to Qoshgar occurs in 1830. During this period of March, the Kokand army was around 40,000 (some sources give it as 60,000-65,000). During this March, the Kokand will achieve a series of victories, but the siege of gulbogh will last 4 months. But other victories are not mentioned in the sources. As a result, Madalikhan sent ambassadors to Beijing. This envoy knew paralelly sent also ambassadors to Russia to receive diplomatic support. As a result of the ambassadorial negotiations, Madalikhan moved about 70,000 qashqars to Fergana. Of madalikhan's second march to Qashqar, local historians give a different view than Russian and Chinese historians. On the eve of the second march, Madalikhan orders Jahongirkhoja's brother Haqquli mingbashi to organize a march, to raise an army. This walk is much more successful for Madalikhan. But the Gulbogkamalilin, the center of the Qoshgar, did not end successfully. Nevertheless, Madalikhan returned from this March with great wealth. Not wanting to stay in qoshgar, the qoshgarites return with them. He downloads the payment of Zakat and Hiraj to people of other religions and converts Buddhist temples into mosques. But

since this information is written many years after this walk, this cannot be said to be so true. The March, while not a great success, was of great political importance. Because a year after the March, i.e. 1832, the proposal to conclude a trade agreement for Kokand that would be beneficial in trade affairs in Qoshgar is expressed by the Chinese government. In accordance with the treaty, the confiscated products of the qawwani merchants, who received the right of Qawwani officials to collect taxes from Muslim merchants, would be returned. Moreover, it is in this year that Madalikhan receives the title of himself –Abulghazikhan, that is, –the father of the struggle for religion. [5. 31-32 B]

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